

Title: Convolutional Attention models for Chat-bots

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INTRODUCTION:

Recently, there has been a massive shift towards chat-bots and conversational agents by the industry worldwide. However, the one problem faced by the industry by and large is the ability to test validity of these systems and how to carry on conversations between multiple domains (open domain). One way to counter this one way is to tag the breakdowns and then handle the domain shifts. Thus we propose end-to-end memory networks for this task, Memory networks have shown to be more effective than LSTMs in question-answering as they are able to store and utilize knowledge over a much longer time.

AIM:

Develop dialogue breakdown analysis and domain analysis using end-to-end memory networks.

RESULTS:

Under evaluation.

CONCLUSIONS:

Under evaluation.

KEYWORDS:

Memory networks; Conversational Interfaces; Attention over Attention networks.

BIOGRAPHY:

Shanky Sharma has completed his Bachelors from University of Pune and has been working in Machine learning since 2013 with various startups and data-science centered teams. He is currently Machine Learning and AI of Scandid, a leading Price-comparison and Deal discovery website and Application.